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A Hypothetical Approach to Sugar Disease Treatment

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ABSTRACT

In the current recent trend, so many diabetes patients' statistics are more visible in almost all hospitals. In this paper one can give a perfect remedy as a working theorem of hypothesis. The addition of Jupiter planet energy for type 2 sugar and the addition of Venus planet energy for type 1 diabetes in the form of food, grain, herbs, flowers, spices, seeds, vegetables, and fruits. Consuming these is not enough, again, friends. Usually, Jupiter and Venus's friends' planets' food consumption is one more kind of treatment for sugar disease. The human body part ruling over the pancreas gland, which gives insulin fluid as hormones, then the natural way of increasing food, such as sweet potato, broccoli, fenugreek, turmeric, etc., and resistance to the flow of glucose through urine is again consuming friends' planets of the Jupiter planet. Even Soul liquid is equivalent to DNA & RNA, resulting in sperm count potency and seminal fluid, which decides the human strength, especially for couples in married life for children's production. Deficiency of Jupiter energy and Venus's energy results in sugar and diabetes disease. Also in a few cases, lifestyle and stressful work environment and heredity for type 2. One can cure through ayurveda methods and gain naturally by consuming food. In the universe there are few negative energy species that are in contact with single-sense-level beings, so this sugar disease will be spreading randomly at peak level. Also, there will be counters for these species as positive energy species, usually 1D sheath species as same as ancestors.

Keywords: *Jupiter planet energy, Venus's planet energy, friends' planets of Jupiter & Venus*

INTRODUCTION

In general, when talking about sugar disease, treatment is about allopathy and ayurveda; of these, ayurveda is a good treatment better than allopathic medicine. In allopathy, long-term consumption of Metformin tablets is advised. But this is not permanent; you need to diet from artificial and natural sweets long-term. But through Ayurveda, one can eat sweet foods limitedly by consuming a few particular foods, herbs, vegetables, fruits, etc. Myrrh, Black seed, Helteet, Fenugreek, Aloes, Artemesia, Cumen, Colocynth, Lupine, Coriander, Rhazya stricta. papaya, amaryllifolius, Kinsenoside, Silymarin, pilosa and polyynes, Berberine, Bitter melon, Cilli pepper and capsaicin, Turmeric, Mate tea, matesaponins, and dicaffeoylquinic, acids, Ginger and gingerol, Soybean, Rooibos, A. vera, Quercetin, Resveratrol.[1-15]

INSULIN RESISTANCE

Licorice and amorfrutins, Dioscorea and polysaccharides, Blueberry and anthocyanins, Astragalus and polysaccharides, G. elata, Cinnamon, Fenugreek, Lychee

In astrology, if rays of Jupiter and Venus are falling on the birth time in the GPS location, then that person has a natural way of gaining positive energy to prevent the sugar disease. If a person's birth chart GPS location shows no rays falling from the planets Jupiter and Venus, then that person surely suffers from sugar disease. So, one can enhance Jupiter and Venus planet energy naturally or artificially to treat the disease. This is the main hypothesis of sugar disease.[16-27]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Enhancing Jupiter Planet foods and Enhancing Venus planet food, also consuming friend planets from Jupiter is sun, moon, mars. If you consume this planet food, then also you will be gaining positive energy which is required to

treatment for sugar type 2 disease. Suppose if you ate the enemy planet of Jupiter food then type 2 disease will go to peak level increasing sugar level. Same way for type 1 Venus friends planets is mercury, rahu, Saturn by consuming this food then type 1 disease will be controlled and prevented. Again, the enemy of these Venus planet food consuming then disease will be increasing sugar diabetes level.

CONCLUSION

- Make strong energy level by Jupiter planet food
- Make strong energy level by Venus planet food
- consuming Friend planet of Jupiter
- consuming Friend planet of Venus
- Use ayurveda treatment
- The addition of Jupiter planet energy for type 2 sugar and the addition of Venus planet energy for type 1 diabetes in the form of food, grain, herbs, flowers, spices, seeds, vegetables, and fruits. Consuming these is not enough, again, friends. Usually Jupiter and Venus's friends' planets' food consumption is one more kind of treatment for sugar disease.
- Effect of Venus planet will be sex organs weaker
- Effects of Jupiter planet will be weaker of pancreas, again insulin hormone imbalance

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